

EGA 2020 presentation publication!

EGA 2020 is the key to correct gas service. Regardless of the manipulations, it shows the real gas measurement values. It has the option of remote reading. We recommend the respected service providers to use gas meters that are equipped with EGA 2020 protection electronics, and you will always see the real gas consumption values and you can easily retrieve any consumption statistics. You can see the value of the minimum and maximum purchase, which helps to determine the base fee correctly.

EGA 2020 is an Electronic Gas Measurement Assistant that can be retrofitted into almost any type of membrane gas meter available in Hungary. The meter retains its original warranty and certified indicators. Its task is to measure the amount of gas passing through the gas meter, i.e. the amount of gas received, detecting possible manipulations, recording data, and remote reading.

EGA 2020 is a small electronic unit with its own communication system. It can be programmed from a computer and read with its own encrypted radio system. Powered by an internal battery, the operating life of more than 10 years is guaranteed, after which the battery can be replaced. Care-free, safe system. EGA 2020 is a unique world innovation, it is located inside the gas meter and its operation is completely independent of the meter.

Its task is to create a measurement result that is completely independent of the counter structure of the gas meters in such a way that it cannot be modified by any undetected manipulation, so the measurement values are suitable for the real accounting of gas measurement and service, for the detection of irregular gas consumption, and also for providing statistical data.

The device consists of the following components:

- Electronic Gas Measurement Assistant
- Optical reflecting unit
- Radio reading unit
- Software communication interface
- Permanent electronic synchronous reader

1.) Electronic Gas Measuring Assistant is a rod with a tamper-proof solid plastic cover. Length 15 centimeters. It houses the sensor unit with optics, the battery, the communication unit and the antenna. The plastic cylinder is cast with explosion-proof synthetic resin, forming a closed compact unit.

2.) The optical unit is a 2X2 cm mirror module that is placed on the gas engine.

3.) The radio reading unit is a USB-connected radio frequency reading module with its own antenna.

4.) The software communication interface is a unique software developed in-house, through which it is possible to read and check the Electronic Gas Measurement Assistant, as well as to query the statistical statements and tables.

5.) Continuous operation Electronic synchronous reading unit for manufacturers and distributors for the first programming. The unit is compatible with the software.

For household categories smaller than G-10 meters, we make versions equipped with the ER18505 EVE battery, and from the G-10 meter type and above, we deliver the device with ULTR LIFE ER26500 batteries.

We are only able to ensure the distribution of the units manufactured by us together with installation.

We provide a 5-year warranty for products manufactured and installed by us, subject to normal use.

The product has contact protection, explosion safety and CE certificates.

For series production, it is recommended to purchase the TG-MES 2020 Gas meter compensation control automation system, which facilitates the initial programming of gas meters. TG-MES 2020 is not part of the offered units, we can provide it with a separate offer.